

Does technology-based non-interactive teaching enhance students' learning in the classroom? ☆

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ABSTRACT

The use of evidence-based practices can be regarded as the gold standard in technology-based learning and instruction. A steadily adopted educational practice is technology-mediated non-interactive teaching, in which students generate explanations of the previously learned contents to a fictitious audience by means of technologies (e.g., video, messenger). Although recent laboratory studies documented benefits of non-interactive teaching, field-oriented evidence is scarce. Research is needed to examine how laboratory evidence applies to authentic learning environments with school students and to determine whether these effects are generalizable to different authentic contexts. We applied a ManyClasses study to a) examine the generalizability of technology-based non-interactive teaching and b) explore context-related (domain, school type), demographical-related (age, gender, language), and implementation-related (grading, medium, timing) boundary conditions. In collaboration with teachers, we realized $k = 20$ different teaching units (each consisting of two lessons) in authentic settings across various school types and domains. Using a within-participants design, school students ($N = 191$) either taught the previously learned contents by means of technology to a fictitious peer or retrieved the contents in mind after the lesson. Results showed no main effect of non-interactive teaching; but domain and school type moderated the learning activity. The findings indicate that non-interactive teaching is not effective per se, but rather depends on the instructional contexts in which it is implemented. The investigation of the teaching effect with new approaches allows, for the first time, more generalizable conclusions to be drawn about non-interactive teaching with technology for students in authentic settings.

Introduction

Particularly in the last years, there has been an increasing interest in how technology-mediated learning activities can be implemented in

asynchronous educational practice to engage students in active and constructive learning processes [1,2]. Based on the generative learning theory [3–5], *generative learning activities* trigger cognitive processes [6], metacognitive processes [7], and motivational processes [4,8], and may

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be optimal activities to enhance learners' active sense-making and generalization of new contents during individual learning phases [3]. A prevalent generative activity in research and practice is non-interactive teaching. Non-interactive teaching is an instructional learning activity in which learners actively generate explanations of the previously learned contents to a non-present and fictitious audience [3]. To allow asynchronous learning, the use of educational technologies, such as videos [9] or messengers [10], enable students to record, save, and send their explanations. The beneficial effects of technology-based non-interactive teaching were documented in recent laboratory studies [11]. Whether these laboratory findings apply to authentic learning environments with school students is, however, still an open question. Research is needed that examines potential effects of non-interactive teaching in authentic learning settings [8,10,12]. More importantly, it is still unclear whether a potential effect holds true in different authentic learning contexts – in other words, whether a potential effect is generalizable to other contexts and if specific boundary conditions determine its effectiveness. To this end, we conducted a ManyClasses study and implemented technology-based non-interactive teaching versus a retrieval activity (free recall-task) across 20 teaching units ($N = 191$ students) and different domains to test the generalizability and additionally examined potential boundary conditions of non-interactive teaching across different lessons.

Non-interactive teaching as a generative activity

Teaching the previously learned contents to a fictitious audience (cf. non-interactive teaching) is a generative learning activity to enhance students' cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational learning [8]. Non-interactive teaching is based on the generative learning theory [4] which claims that generative activities, such as non-interactive teaching, enable students to construct knowledge by actively integrating new information to their prior knowledge (see also [3], for a recent review). Generative activities support students in deep (meta-)cognitive processes [4], and at the same time may enhance students' motivational orientations [8,12].

These assumptions are in line with seminal frameworks such as the Select-Organize-Integrate (SOI) model [4] which presents three different steps to support students in engaging in deep cognitive processes. Students first need to prepare themselves to be able to teach the learned contents by *selecting* the most relevant information of a lesson or a provided text they aim to explain. Second, they need to *organize* the selected information in a coherent order to be able to make sense out of the provided contents and for structuring their explanation. Third, the *integration* of the new learned contents with their prior knowledge allows students to deeply process the contents, to make inferences between the new and prior knowledge structures and to be able to provide examples and further elaborations which go beyond the given contents [3].

In addition to these cognitive processes, non-interactive teaching is regarded to trigger meta-cognitive processes, such as monitoring one's own understanding (cf. monitoring accuracy [7]) and detect potential knowledge gaps [4], but also motivational processes, as the act of teaching to a fictitious audience may enhance students' basic psychological needs (e.g., perceived competence, autonomy, relatedness [13]) compared to rather self-referential tasks with lower levels of communication.

Using technology allows an asynchronous implementation of non-interactive teaching. Hoogerheide, Visee et al. [12], for instance, applied non-interactive teaching as a homework assignment. School students were asked to teach the previous learned contents to a fictitious peer at home by generating an explanatory video, which then could be saved and sent to the teacher. In comparison to analog learning activities, technology-based non-interactive teaching might even increase the feeling of a social presence of the fictitious peer, since they need to record their explanations within social environments, such as messengers.

The feeling of a social presence is considered a crucial component for the effectiveness of teaching (c.f. social presence hypothesis [14]). In sum, without the use of technology, teachers were not able to receive, track, and evaluate students' generated explanations.

Effectiveness of non-interactive teaching

Fiorella and Mayer [15] started to explore the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching by conducting two experiments. They assigned participants to study either with the intention to answer questions after the learning phase (control condition) or with the intention to teach. Half of the students who studied with the intention to teach answered questions afterwards (teaching expectancy condition) whereas the other half actually taught the learned contents (teaching condition). Results demonstrated effects of teaching expectancy and non-interactive teaching compared to the control condition on immediate and delayed learning outcomes. Since the study by Fiorella and Mayer [15], the effect of non-interactive teaching has been steadily investigated by the research community [9,14,16–18].

Additionally, few studies provided evidence that non-interactive teaching enhances students' monitoring accuracy (accuracy of judging one's own current knowledge). For instance, in the study by Fukaya [7], the students studied the learning materials with the intention to teach the contents and then either taught the contents (teaching condition) or continued with the knowledge test (expect to teach condition). Students in the control condition studied the texts with the intention to write keywords. Before answering the posttest, students rated their current knowledge by estimating how many points they would receive in the posttest (judgment of learning). Students monitoring accuracy was estimated by using Goodman-Kruskal gamma association between their judgment of learning and their actual score in the posttest. Results showed a large main effect of students' monitoring accuracy. Students who taught the contents judged their knowledge more precisely than students in both other conditions (see [19], for related findings).

Moreover, initial research has been conducted that demonstrated beneficial effects of technology-based non-interactive teaching on students' perceived enjoyment. Hoogerheide, Visee et al. [12], for instance, showed that non-interactive teaching was not only effective regarding students' learning but also increased their enjoyment during the learning activity, as potential proxy for intrinsic motivation.

The effect of technology-based non-interactive teaching was also documented in recent meta-analytic studies [8,11,14,16,20–22]. For instance, Ribosa and Duran [11] included 23 articles in their analysis which contained 62 comparisons between a teaching condition and a control condition. The findings showed a small, significant effect of teaching compared to the control condition.

In addition to laboratory studies, to date, only two field studies documented the effect of technology-based non-interactive teaching in field settings [10,12]. For instance, Hoogerheide, Visee et al. [12] examined the effect of non-interactive teaching during a homework assignment on photosynthesis and contrasted non-interactive teaching to summarization and restudy. Results showed that technology-based non-interactive teaching was more effective than restudy, but not more effective than summarizing. Jacob et al. [10] conducted a field-experiment in biology (photosynthesis) and compared two non-interactive teaching modes (written or audio messaging) to a retrieval condition to keep the amount of retrieval processes constant across conditions. Contrarily to Hoogerheide, Visee et al. [12], the authors did not obtain a main effect of technology-based non-interactive teaching. Additional moderation analyses, however, revealed benefits of technology-based non-interactive teaching for students with low levels of academic self-concept.

The ManyClasses approach

Even though prior research demonstrated small but significant

effects of non-interactive teaching, most of the studies have been conducted in laboratory settings, with university students, and were not embedded in real classroom situations. Research approaches are needed, which go beyond classic laboratory studies and implementations within one topic to test the generalizability of non-interactive teaching across different contexts in authentic classroom settings [23]. Fyfe et al. [24] proposed the ManyClasses approach, which may be suitable to fill this gap.

In the ManyClasses approach, a common experimental comparison is implemented across a variety of topics, teacher implementations, learning materials, subjects, and student samples which may help to understand whether distinct findings of educational practices, such as non-interactive teaching, are generalizable and/or whether the findings are determined by additional factors [14,24,25]. To ensure that the study's experimental design and educational practices are implemented as intended in real-world classroom settings, co-constructive activities with the participating teachers are required to increase implementation fidelity – that is, fidelity to the experimental procedures and conditions outlined in the study design [23]. Fyfe and colleagues [24], for instance, examined the effect of the timing of system-provided feedback on students' knowledge acquisition. They conducted a within-participants design and randomly assigned students to a set of treatment orders per class assignment (delayed feedback followed by immediate feedback versus immediate feedback followed by delayed feedback). Furthermore, the authors varied on the class-level whether students received an incentive or not. This framework was implemented in 38 different classrooms of various disciplines (e.g., history, chemistry, psychology). Surprisingly, the authors did not find an effect of delayed versus immediate feedback and study incentives. Preregistered moderation analyses of 40 different moderators did not obtain strong evidence for systematic interactions. The findings highlight that experimental findings are not generally transferable into real classroom settings with less experimental control. At the same time, the findings may also be interpreted in terms of a need of a careful collaboration with educational practice to effectively implement experimental set-ups in schools.

The ManyClasses approach can particularly work well together with co-designs, as co-designs consider and support the active role of teachers in authentic settings [23]. Co-designs are a valuable approach which equally considers perspectives of educational practice and educational research [26,27]. Co-design approaches avoid researcher-led “top-down approaches”, as they consider and integrate teachers' everyday practices by actively involving them as agents in the design process, which are relevant to understand the conditions in which the experimental set-up is implemented [28]. Thus, teachers are seen as professional contributors and sources of educational innovation [28] which contribute to more applicable innovations [26].

The present study

The aim of the present study was to test the generalizability of non-interactive teaching by implementing it in diverse contexts and to explore its potential boundary conditions. To achieve this goal, we adopted a *ManyClasses*-approach [24]. Following Lachner et al. [23], we closely collaborated in total with $N = 39$ schoolteachers and pre-service teachers, who were enrolled in a post-professional Master course of a university in Southwestern Germany to localize non-interactive teaching implementations in subject-specific teaching. The schoolteachers taught in different schools (i.e., primary school, middle school, high school, and vocational school) and different domains (i.e., STEM, humanities, languages) with different student populations.

Within this study, the schoolteachers and pre-service teachers closely worked together in design teams ($N = 10$ teams). Each design team consisted of one experienced schoolteacher, a researcher, and two to three pre-service teachers and planned two lessons and additionally developed comprehension tests that were closely aligned with the learning goals [24,29]. The schoolteachers carefully selected the two

lessons which differed in their contents but were comparable in their complexity. Then, the schoolteachers taught both planned lessons to their students in school within the regular curriculum. As we conducted a field experiment with learning activity as a within-participants factor (technology-based non-interactive teaching versus retrieval), teachers asked their school students to either teach (via audio or video) or to retrieve the previously learned contents as individual consolidation activity. Those, who taught the contents in the first lesson, retrieved the contents in the second lesson and vice versa. We tested technology-based non-interactive teaching against a retrieval practice activity (free recall task) to control for retrieval effects, since teaching also includes retrieval processes [3]. Retrieval practice activities have shown to be effective learning strategies to promote students' learning [30–32]. Even though teaching and retrieval practice trigger different underlying processes [33], both are considered as generative learning strategies [4,34]. We therefore consider retrieval practice as a strong control condition.

We investigated the following preregistered hypotheses in our study (see https://aspredicted.org/H6L_QL8):

Is Technology-Based Non-Interactive Teaching Effective? First, we investigated effects of technology-based non-interactive teaching across instructional contexts. Based on previous evidence (e.g. [11,21]), we a) hypothesized that students who are engaged in technology-based non-interactive teaching would outperform students who retrieve the contents (learning-outcome-hypothesis). Additionally, we hypothesized that technology-based non-interactive teaching would result in more accurate monitoring judgments as compared to retrieval (monitoring-accuracy-hypothesis). Further, we explored whether non-interactive teaching will also result in higher levels of enjoyment, as an indicator of intrinsic motivation (enjoyment-hypothesis), as the social scenario of non-interactive teaching of a fictitious peer may result in higher levels of basic psychological needs (e.g., competence, relatedness, and autonomy).

How Robust is Technology-Based Non-interactive Teaching across Contexts? In addition to our main research questions, we explored the robustness of technology-based non-interactive teaching across different contexts. We investigated the influence of see [24], for similar analyses on the timing of feedback) as potential boundary conditions of our implementations.

Method

Participants and design

Ten classes with 191 school students from different school types (primary school, middle school, high school, vocational school) participated in the study in Southwestern Germany (see Table 1 for more details). The recruited sample size exceeded the required sample size of 140 students, determined by using an a-priori power analysis to be able to detect small to medium effects with a power 80 % (see preregistration: https://aspredicted.org/H6L_QL8). The school students were on average 14 years old ($M = 14.40$, $SD = 4.23$) and 45 % of the students were female. Most of the students were either German native speakers or grew up bilingually with German (85 %). Only few students stated to have another native language than German (15 %). We conducted a field-experiment with two conditions (teaching versus retrieval) as within-participants factor and used a posttest-only design [24] to reduce the amount of testing across the classes, and as within-participants are able to control for intra-individual variance.

Measures

Comprehension Posttest. Teachers and researchers co-designed a comprehension posttest for each lesson which were comparably difficult within the respective subject. All tests comprised five open-ended questions [25]. Students received one point for a correct answer and a half point if their answer was partly correct (5 points in total). Twenty

Table 1
Overview of all classes.

Class ID	Students per Class	Cohort	School	Grade Level	Students Mean Age	Subject	Domain	Topic 1	Topic 2
1	21	1	Middle school	9	14.62 (0.66)	Physics	STEM	Electric generator	Transformer
2	18	1	High school	12	17.33 (1.51)	Biochemistry	STEM	Meiosis	Chromosomal translocation
3	32	1	Middle school	10	15.45 (0.62)	Mathematics	STEM	Geometry: Line	Geometry: Space
4	16	2	Primary school	4	9.28 (0.46)	Science	STEM	Water cycle	Cloud formation
5	22	2	Middle school	10	18.41 (2.34)	Occupational safety for technicians	Humanities	Occupational safety and health	Youth-Protection Act
6	24	1	Vocational school	1. year	18.65 (0.64)	Economics	Humanities	Collective bargaining	Work council
7	14	1	Primary school	3	7.89 (0.42)	Religion	Humanities	Zacchaeus	Healing the deaf mute
8	9	1	High school	13	18.67 (0.49)	History	Humanities	Relationship between East & West Germany	German reunification
9	14	2	Middle school	9	14.46 (0.51)	English	Languages	Reading comprehension 1	Reading comprehension 2
10	21	2	Primary school	2	7.33 (0.48)	German	Languages	Fairy tales	Recipes

Note. Middle schools include grade levels from 5 to 10. High schools include grade levels from 11 to 13.

percent of the answers were coded by two independent raters. Since the interrater reliability was very good between both raters ($ICC_{2,1} \geq 0.84$, see Table 2 for details), one rater coded the remaining answers. The reliability of most of the tests was good (McDonald's $\omega_t > .70$, see Table 2 for more details).

Monitoring Accuracy. To analyze students' monitoring accuracy, we asked them to judge their performance before answering the comprehension test on a scale from zero points to five points. The item was based on Baars et al. [35]: "You will now complete a questionnaire with five tasks on the topic 'Generator'. You will receive one point for each correct answer, so that you can score a maximum of five points in total. How many points do you think you will score?". We calculated students' accuracy by using bias which measures the difference between the predicted and actual score (i.e., $x_{\text{Judgment}} - x_{\text{Performance}}$ [35]). Thus, we subtracted students' actual performance from their judgments. This estimation allowed us to identify an overestimation (positive values), an underestimation (negative values), and an accurate estimation (value of zero).

Enjoyment. We used the short scale by Jacob et al. [36] to assess students' perceived enjoyment after the learning activity (teaching versus retrieving) by two items (e.g., I enjoyed teaching"). Students rated their enjoyment on a scale from 1 "not at all" to 4 "absolutely" ($\alpha = .73$).

Mental Effort. Students were instructed to rate their perceived mental effort after the learning activity (teaching versus retrieving) with

an item adapted from Paas [37]: "How much mental effort did you invest in teaching the material?", on a 9-point Likert scale from "very little" to "very much".

Procedure

We first received approval to conduct the study from the council of governments and from all school principals of the participating schools to conduct our study and obtained written consent from students and their parents to collect the data. Data collection took place in 2022 and in 2023 by teachers who attended a seminar at university in South-western Germany. Both seminars were embedded within a Master program for experienced schoolteachers and pre-service teachers. Within these seminars, the teacher collaboratively worked together in small groups (3-4 students) and developed two comparably difficult lessons within a subject (e.g., electric generator and transformer in Physics, see Table 1 for more details). In several weekly small group discussions and reciprocal feedback loops, they designed the teaching unit by determining the learning objectives and selecting the needed materials. Additionally, they collaboratively developed a comprehension test with the research project team for both lessons. After the lessons and tests were finalized, one teacher per group taught the lessons to his or her regular school class (duration: 45 minutes). After the lesson, students who provided written consent either taught the learned contents to a fictitious peer by means of technology (audio or video message) or

Table 2
Summary of descriptive statistics across classes and conditions.

	Learning Outcome						Monitoring Accuracy						Reliability		Rater Reliability	
	OV		RP		TE		OV		RP		TE		(Omega)		(ICC)	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	Test 1	Test 2	Test 1	Test 2
STEM																
Physics	1.82	1.35	1.50	1.12	2.06	1.50	0.18	1.38	0.00	1.60	0.31	1.22	1.00	0.99	0.89	0.84
Biochemistry	2.58	1.00	2.44	1.12	2.73	0.86	1.13	1.37	1.00	1.37	1.27	1.40	0.79	0.73	0.94	0.87
Mathematics	3.30	1.01	3.45	0.87	3.14	1.12	-0.13	0.97	-0.23	0.79	-0.02	1.13	0.66	0.71	0.89	0.98
Science	3.12	1.01	3.25	0.94	3.03	1.07	0.16	1.05	0.25	1.08	0.09	1.07	0.88	0.76	0.92	0.87
Humanities																
Occ. safety	1.96	0.90	1.72	0.80	2.15	0.95	2.01	1.27	2.47	1.22	1.65	1.22	0.60	0.70	0.99	0.94
Economics	3.13	0.99	2.63	0.93	3.63	0.79	0.07	1.16	0.20	1.09	-0.07	1.24	0.75	0.77	0.91	0.94
Religion	2.74	0.88	2.62	0.88	2.86	0.90	1.78	1.12	1.88	0.74	1.68	1.45	0.53	0.74	0.89	0.92
History	2.09	1.02	1.50	1.00	2.43	0.93	0.27	1.21	0.75	1.89	0.00	0.65	0.92	1.00	0.91	1.00
Languages																
English	2.25	0.96	2.09	0.94	2.41	1.00	1.75	0.80	1.73	0.56	1.77	1.01	0.65	0.82	0.94	0.96
German	4.15	0.70	4.28	0.62	4.02	0.77	-0.46	1.51	-0.32	1.25	-0.60	1.74	0.36	0.69	0.98	0.94

Note. OV = Overall, RP = Retrieval practice, TE = Teaching.

retrieved the contents (control condition). The learning activity was either applied at the end of the lesson or as a homework assignment, which made the use of technology essential, since it allowed students to record their explanations. Regardless of the timing, all students used technology to record their video or audio messages.

Afterwards, students completed the posttest which contained demographical questions (age, gender, native language), questions regarding the learning activity (enjoyment, effort), judgments of learning, and the comprehension test. The teachers repeated this procedure with the second lesson after one or two weeks. This time, students who taught in the first lesson retrieved the contents and students who retrieved the contents taught the contents to a fictitious peer.

Students who taught received the following instruction based on Jacob et al. [19]:

Explain what you have learned in today's lesson as well and as comprehensively as you can. Try not only to reproduce the learned contents but also include examples and your own thoughts. Prepare your explanation and record it with your device when you are ready. You have a total of 10 minutes to complete the task.

Students received the following instruction, also based on Jacob et al. [19]:

Retrieve what you have learned in today's lesson. You may take notes. You have 10 minutes to complete the task.

Data analyses

Since we applied a within-participants design, missing data occurred naturally. We used multiple imputations with 10 iterations and 10 data sets to deal with missing values [38]. Missing data were estimated based on the distribution of the available variables. We used the R-package *mice* ([39]; version 3.8.0) to impute the missing values. We performed multiple regressions with comprehension, monitoring accuracy, and enjoyment as dependent variables and learning activity (i.e., non-interactive teaching versus retrieval) as independent variable. As we had a nested structure, we applied cluster-robust estimations of fixed effect models to account for the correlated error terms within a cluster (students within classes within cohorts) but independent error terms across clusters [40].

Results

We used standardized β -coefficients and η^2_p as effect size (small effects: $\eta^2_p = .01$, $\beta = 0.20$; medium effects: $\eta^2_p = .06$, $\beta = 0.50$; large effects: $\eta^2_p = .14$, $\beta = 0.80$). We set the alpha level to $\alpha = .05$. Preliminary analyses showed no significant differences between conditions regarding age, $F(1, 380) = 0.00$, $p = .983$, $\eta^2_p = .00$, gender, $\chi^2(2) = 0.01$, $p = .994$, $\eta^2_p = .00$, and language proficiency, $\chi^2(1) = 0.15$, $p = .701$, $\eta^2_p = .00$, indicating that student characteristics were comparable among conditions.

Was non-interactive teaching more effective than retrieval?

In a first step, we investigated whether non-interactive teaching was more effective in authentic classroom settings than retrieval in terms of cognitive (learning outcomes), metacognitive (monitoring accuracy), and motivational outcomes (enjoyment). Contrarily, to our hypotheses, results indicated no significant differences between conditions regarding learning outcomes, $\beta = 0.13$, $p = .178$, monitoring accuracy, $\beta = -0.11$, $p = .456$, and enjoyment, $\beta = .01$, $p = .960$. Apparently, non-interactive teaching was not significantly effective in general across contexts (see Table 2, for the descriptive statistics). Notably, the variance was considerably high among teaching units, indicating that teaching might depend on additional factors.

Which factors influenced non-interactive teaching?

The high variance within the descriptive data suggested considerable heterogeneity among subjects. To better understand the potential boundary conditions of non-interactive teaching versus retrieval, in a next step, we inspected potential boundary conditions via moderation analyses (see Appendix A for the detailed analyses). Results revealed a significant interaction of domain and the learning activity: Interestingly, non-interactive teaching was only more effective than retrieval in humanities ($\beta = 0.46$, $p = .031$, small to medium effect) but not in STEM or languages subjects (see Fig. 1, see also Appendix A for detailed results). Domain did neither moderate students' monitoring accuracy nor their enjoyment (see Appendix A for detailed results).

Additionally, the school type moderated the learning activity: Non-interactive teaching was more effective than retrieval for high school students ($\beta = 0.48$, $p = .044$, small to medium effect) but not for the other school types (see Fig. 2, see also Appendix A for detailed results). The school type did neither moderate students' monitoring accuracy nor their enjoyment (see Appendix A for detailed results).

Regarding students' demographic characteristics (age, gender, language) and the implementation of non-interactive teaching (grading, medium, timing), none of the moderators reached significance – neither regarding students' learning outcomes nor their monitoring accuracy and their enjoyment (see Appendix A for detailed results).

Discussion

The aim of the current study was twofold. First, we aimed at testing the generalizability of the effect of technology-based non-interactive teaching in a set of diverse authentic school contexts. Second, we explored potential instructional context-related and student-related boundary conditions that may determine the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching. To this end, we applied the ManyClasses approach [24] and collaboratively worked with experienced teachers who implemented non-interactive teaching versus retrieval as consolidation activity after their lesson in school. The findings can be summarized as follows:

First, our results revealed that technology-based non-interactive teaching was not generally effective, as we did not obtain a main effect of non-interactive teaching compared to retrieval activities regarding students' (meta-)cognitive and motivational outcomes across implementations. This finding raises the question of how the non-interactive teaching task needs to be designed and implemented in order to provide students with effective learning strategies that enhance their learning. Pre-trainings before teaching [41], specific prompts [42,43] or providing feedback on students' explanations [44] may be possibilities to make the non-interactive teaching task more effective in general. That

Fig. 1. Domain Moderated Non-Interactive Teaching

Note. Plots are based on row data and presents means, standard error, data points, and the distribution of the sample.

Fig. 2. School Type Moderated Non-Interactive Teaching
Note. Plots are based on row data and presents means, standard error, data points, and the distribution of the sample.

said also the expectancy to teach can increase the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching and therefore should be implemented in future research [21]. Finally, we would like to note that we tested technology-based non-interactive teaching against retrieval practice activity. Retrieval practice has been shown to be effective in terms of learning [30–32] and therefore can be considered as a strong control condition which may explain the obtained null findings. Future research should investigate the effectiveness of technology-based non-interactive teaching compared to non-generative strategies, such as restudying. Relatedly, technology-based non-interactive teaching can be supported by additional retrieval practice tasks to increase its effectiveness [33].

Second, we explored potential boundary conditions that may determine the effectiveness of non-interactive teaching. One crucial boundary condition was the domain in which the non-interactive teaching task was implemented. Technology-based non-interactive teaching was more effective in the humanities than in STEM or language subjects. First, this finding is interesting since most prior research on non-interactive teaching has been mainly implemented in STEM subjects [9,18] and often resulted in non-significant or mixed results [14]. Thus, it may be that technology-based non-interactive teaching is not effective in STEM and languages, as they primarily address procedural contents that rather required rule acquisition and automation [8]. Hence, non-interactive teaching might prove to be more effective in the humanities, which often realize a more discourse-oriented teaching style which enhances the fit of the learning activity to the content [45]. Nevertheless, this conclusion is highly speculative and requires replication studies that explicitly manipulate the type of the learning content (conceptual versus procedural).

That said, school type moderated the non-interactive teaching effect as well. Our results indicated that generating a non-interactive explanation was not effective for primary or middle school students but for high school students. This finding is partly in line with prior research which documented that (self-)explaining is less effective for primary and middle school students compared to university students [10,46]. From a developmental perspective, younger students may not have the necessary prerequisites to take the alternative perspective of a fictitious peer and adopt one's knowledge to the needs of a less-knowledgeable peer during non-interactive teaching [8,34]. The question arises how learning by non-interactive teaching can be improved as a learning activity in order to also support students in lower levels of education and needs to be addressed in future research. However, it must be noted that age was no relevant boundary condition, suggesting that the effect cannot be attributed to the age as a proxy of their (meta-)cognitive development, but probably to differences of classroom compositions. None of the other boundary conditions were significant.

Overall, (to our knowledge) our study is the first in which the generalizability of non-interactive teaching has been investigated in

authentic classroom settings. By using a ManyClasses approach, we were able to test non-interactive teaching across different contexts and settings and to explore potential boundary conditions and therefore contribute to prior research that mainly investigated non-interactive teaching in isolated, laboratory settings with specific learning materials. Thus, our findings contribute to the scarce evidence that ManyClasses studies may be a sensitive tool to examine the generalizability of intervention effects in the classroom.

Study limitations and future research

One limitation is related to the field-character of our study. Field experiments have higher risks of less control and inattentive behavior of the participants [47,48]. Additionally, we were not able to control for fine details of how the learning strategies were implemented. Such details, however, may be crucial factors regarding potential learning effects. To reduce such potential differences and interfering factors, we provided all teachers with the same guidelines and instructions, aiming at increasing the likelihood of same implementations. Relatedly, the control of the teaching materials is also very limited in ManyClasses approaches, since teachers are regarded as the experts who are responsible to design the materials [24]. Nevertheless, we particularly decided to test non-interactive teaching in the field to investigate its effectiveness in authentic settings which we consider as a strength of our study.

Additionally, we were not able to collect and analyze students' generated explanations since they were part of the regular classroom setting and implemented in the school specific tools which underly distinct data protection (see also [12], for related restrictions). Analyzing students' explanations would provide more details in students' underlying processes during the learning activities and even might explain differences regarding the effectiveness among domains. Jacob et al. [19] for instance demonstrated that students who generated an explanation perceived the situation during the task as more social than students who retrieved the contents. Higher level of social awareness led students to generate richer explanations by teaching concepts which resulted in higher learning outcomes. As another example, Lachner et al. [49] demonstrated that students who generated an oral non-interactive explanation elaborated more during the learning activity than students who wrote an explanation. Thus, analyzing students' explanations as process data would allow us further explorations. Future research should therefore explore process data as potential mediators, particularly in humanities.

Relatedly, it is still unclear whether teaching was not more effective than retrieving in general. Non-interactive teaching may only be a result of retrieving the contents during teaching. Nevertheless, we obtained significant benefits of technology-based non-interactive teaching compared to retrieval in specific contexts (i.e., domain, school type). Since we do not have data on the quality of the explanations, the null finding may be traced back to a low quality of students' generated explanations, indicating that students who learned in different learning settings needed different instructions and additional support during generating a non-interactive explanation. Again, further studies are needed which focus on instructing students to generate high quality explanations, for example by using prompts or feedback [41,43].

Finally, we would like to draw attention to our moderation analyses which need to be interpreted with caution, as testing specific subsets may have decreased the statistical power. Even though we exceeded the required sample size with over 35 %, future research is needed that replicates our findings with an even higher statistical power.

Conclusion

To our knowledge, this study is the first to investigate the generalizability of technology-based non-interactive teaching by adopting the ManyClasses approach and a co-design. These approaches allowed us to

test the effectiveness of the learning activity in diverse and authentic settings. Results indicated the potential role of domain and school type, suggesting that technology-based non-interactive teaching may be particularly effective in humanities and in high schools. In humanities, the discourse-oriented nature of the subject may complement the explanatory process inherent in non-interactive teaching, fostering deeper conceptual understanding. Similarly, the efficacy in high schools could be attributed to students' greater cognitive and metacognitive maturity, enabling them to benefit more from self-directed learning activities like teaching. These results provide crucial first insights into the factors influencing the success of learning by teaching. Future studies should build on these findings by exploring further contextual variables and refining the instructional design of non-interactive teaching to maximize its potential across different subjects and educational levels. Such efforts will help to establish a more comprehensive understanding of how and when this learning strategy can be most effectively implemented.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Summary of the Explorative Moderation Analyses regarding Learning Outcome and Monitoring Accuracy

	β	se	p
Domain as Moderator			
Learning Outcome			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.03	.15	.813
Domain: Humanities	-0.14	.16	.392
Domain: Languages	0.55	.23	.020
Learning activity × Humanities	0.46	.21	.031
Learning activity × Languages	0.08	.23	.724
Monitoring Accuracy			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.08	.21	.699
Domain: Humanities	0.14	.19	.459
Domain: Languages	-0.07	.23	.752
Learning activity × Humanities	-0.02	.26	.953
Learning activity × Languages	-0.09	.26	.719
Enjoyment			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	0.06	0.17	.744
Domain: Humanities	0.42	0.17	.017
Domain: Languages	0.44	0.22	.046
Learning activity × Humanities	-0.02	0.22	.938
Learning activity × Languages	-0.24	0.26	.365
School Type as Moderator			
Learning Outcome			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.01	.15	.937
School type: Middle school	-0.56	.20	.006
School type: High school	-0.74	.19	< .001
School type: Vocational school	-1.16	.26	< .001
Learning activity × Middle school	-0.02	.23	.935
Learning activity × High school	0.48	.24	.044
Learning activity × Vocational school	0.18	.32	.579
Monitoring Accuracy			

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	β	se	p
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.22	.19	.256
School type: Middle school	-0.09	.22	.668
School type: High school	0.06	.23	.803
School type: Vocational school	0.98	.30	.002
Learning activity \times Middle school	0.27	.24	.267
Learning activity \times High school	0.12	.28	.662
Learning activity \times Vocational school	-0.12	.35	.733
Enjoyment			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.03	0.21	.903
School type: Middle school	-0.82	0.18	< .001
School type: High school	-0.61	0.21	.004
School type: Vocational school	-1.15	0.29	< .001
Learning activity \times Middle school	0.05	0.25	.849
Learning activity \times High school	0.12	0.27	.666
Learning activity \times Vocational school	-0.15	0.35	.662
Grading as Moderator			
Learning Outcome			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	0.00	.11	.977
Reward	-0.68	.16	< .001
Learning activity \times Reward	0.37	.21	.076
Monitoring Accuracy			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.06	.13	.626
Reward	0.24	.20	.241
Learning activity \times Reward	-0.12	.22	.581
Enjoyment			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.03	0.14	.812
Reward	-0.62	0.17	.001
Learning activity \times Reward	0.12	0.19	.547
Medium as Moderator			
Learning Outcome			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.04	.11	.723
Medium (Audio = 0; Video = 1)	-0.79	.15	< .001
Learning activity \times Medium	0.36	.20	.073
Monitoring Accuracy			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.09	.13	.484
Medium (Audio = 0; Video = 1)	0.33	.24	.190
Learning activity \times Medium	-0.03	.23	.904
Enjoyment			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.03	0.14	.834
Medium (Audio = 0; Video = 1)	-0.43	0.21	.058
Learning activity \times Medium	0.08	0.20	.693
Timing as Moderator			
Learning Outcome			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	0.22	.15	.145
Timing (After lesson = 0; Homework = 1)	0.14	.16	.409
Learning activity \times Timing	-0.18	.24	.471
Monitoring Accuracy			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.08	.20	.686
Timing (After lesson = 0; Homework = 1)	-0.14	.18	.433
Learning activity \times Timing	-0.04	.25	.866
Enjoyment			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	0.02	0.16	.896
Timing (After lesson = 0; Homework = 1)	-0.10	0.18	.595
Learning activity \times Timing	-0.03	0.24	.909
Language as Moderator			
Learning Outcome			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	0.11	.11	.310
Language	-0.46	.21	.032
Learning activity \times Language	0.10	.26	.686
Monitoring Accuracy			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.16	.15	.305
Language	-0.03	.23	.894
Learning activity \times Language	0.39	.31	.218
Enjoyment			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.01	0.14	.955
Language	-0.61	0.18	< .001
Learning activity \times Language	0.02	0.31	.958
Age as Moderator			
Learning Outcome			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	0.13	.10	.174
Age	-0.34	.07	< .001
Learning activity \times Age	0.14	.09	.119
Monitoring Accuracy			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.11	.14	.456
Age	0.10	.09	.267
Learning activity \times Age	0.04	.10	.720

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	β	se	p
Enjoyment			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	0.01	0.12	.956
Age	-0.33	0.07	< .001
Learning activity \times Age	0.00	0.10	.974
Gender as Moderator			
Learning Outcome			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	0.16	.13	.237
Gender (Male = 1; Female = 2)	0.16	.16	.315
Learning activity \times Gender	-0.02	.19	.938
Monitoring Accuracy			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.11	.22	.627
Gender (Male = 1; Female = 2)	-0.16	.20	.436
Learning activity \times Gender	-0.03	.28	.905
Enjoyment			
Learning activity (Retrieval = 0; Explaining = 1)	-0.06	0.21	.768
Gender (Male = 1; Female = 2)	0.47	0.18	.014
Learning activity \times Gender	0.15	0.26	.581

Note. Significant results are highlighted in bold letters. We excluded the category “diverse” in the gender moderator analyses since only four participants chose this category.

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